
BASIC TECHNIQUES AND TECHNOLOGIES USED IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract.

In the developed period of our society, it is desirable to make the educational process more interesting and meaningful for listeners, not limited to previous methodological manuals, but using it with the help of scientific and technical innovations, the Internet and high technology. Today in our country great attention is paid to the development of computer technology and the Internet. Accordingly, along with computer science and new information technologies, the teaching of subjects related to vocational education in educational institutions remains a requirement of the time.

Key words.

Distance learning, information technologies, teaching aids, internet, programs.

The introduction of new technologies in education has led to the emergence of new educational technologies and forms of teaching based on electronic means of information transmission and processing. The following technical means and technologies are used in distance learning: trainer, tester and means of communication. Teaching aids include glossaries, search tools, e-textbooks, video lectures and more. Test tools include test questions, self-tests. The means of communication are forums, mail, audio and video cassettes. The traditional course of lectures in traditional teaching involves: lectures, comments (interpretation of the study material by the speaker), assessment in the oral, final exam. In distance education, the function of the teacher is performed by teaching and testing tools (fully automated, complete software products), as well as video and electronically published teaching materials that create an automated learning environment. The possibilities of the electronic textbook can be expanded with the use of modern means of animation and video equipment.

These can be video lectures on the course, demonstrations of production processes, speeches of famous scientists, etc. When creating an electronic textbook, you need to create a database and enter data into it. In this case, there are some ways to access the database and perform actions on the materials contained in it.

Didactic programs for modern computers (electronic textbooks, computer assignments, multimedia electronic textbooks, hypertext information systems, electronic archives, electronic catalogs, reference books, encyclopedias, test and formative training programs) multimedia teaching aids.

Today, it is important to create an information environment for the educational institution. If it is not possible to connect all computer classrooms of higher education institutions to the Internet and at the same time use the information available on the Internet, including electronic textbooks, it is possible to create an Internet space of a higher education institution operating in a local area network. The Internet to be created consists of a set of information, such as a didactic portfolio of space sciences, an individual portfolio of teachers. We will focus on the introduction of a new information-based educational system in higher education, the introduction of the Internet - the space of higher education, the placement of electronic textbooks in it and the scientific and theoretical basis of distance learning forms and methods.

The development of new teaching technologies aimed at improving the quality of fundamental training of students is also a key direction in the modernization of modern higher education in a rapidly changing information society. Recently, there has been a widespread belief that computer technology can be used primarily in organizations, banks or research institutes. At present, there are different views and suggestions on the concept of "information education system". Based on the materials of the Federation of Internet Education, it can be defined as follows: Information environment in an educational institution is a set of specially organized components that ensure the integration of information technology systems aimed at improving the efficiency of the educational process. The Internet Space Coordination Center consists of a repository of software for use in various services of the higher education institution. It will be necessary to create a set of special software technologies to automate the work of the management process, information analysis and reporting.

The methodological support of science lessons is given schematically below. Methodical support of science lessons. The control unit is designed for various control tests on methodical support. The educational block or didactic portfolio on a subject consists of:

- curricula and programs;
- textbooks and manuals;
- traditional printed teaching aids;

- codograms;
- slides;
- educational films;
- tables;
- didactic materials for teaching;
- training equipment;
- multimedia lesson plans;
- training and control software;
- virtual laboratories;
- Electronic encyclopedias and dictionaries.

The didactic portfolio of disciplines should be constantly updated and replenished. It can be done in electronic form with a finished product or by creating a custom product. It should be noted that in addition to the finished product in electronic form, it is important to replenish the didactic portfolio with educational products made in the educational institution. This, in turn, opens up the possibilities of the educational institution in the first place and allows students to take a differentiated approach.

The use of modern Internet technology in this project is very important. While working on the project, some students learn the language of hypertext HTML, so the result of the project is created in the form of a Web page. On the basis of these software, the educational institution prepares electronic textbooks, virtual laboratory work in certain disciplines. The program should be written in such a way that users on adjacent computers do not get the same result. In addition, the created software product should allow the teacher to monitor every activity of the student. In the process of practical work, a control file containing the results of the experiment is created. After the lesson, the teacher should be able to review these files and compare them with the relevant results.

Another practical aspect of this type of software is that it is suitable for distance learning. In addition to replenishing the didactic portfolio with the necessary materials in the field of science, general information about the teachers of the educational institution, pedagogical experience, information, information on professional development, achievements, published information. it is also important to include methodological materials. Another important aspect of creating an Internet environment in higher education is the psychological and pedagogical support of students. Informed resources allow students to study the characteristics of their character not only with questionnaires or psychological tests,

but also with students and parents. It should also help to organize psychological counseling services for mothers. This type of service involves students and parents who, for some unknown reason, do not ask questions directly to the psychologist. They can communicate directly with the computer and get answers to their questions.

So, the process of distance learning should be organized on the basis of such pedagogical technologies that students should have the following opportunities:

To acquire the necessary fundamental knowledge that can be applied to the solution of specific scientific or practical problems;

To solve problems with friends in the process of learning;

To work with additional sources of information necessary to address the issues;

Overcoming all existing problems, applying the acquired knowledge in practice;

Carrying out independent observations using Internet technologies;

To be able to assess their level of knowledge, achievements, to adjust their activities.

In conclusion, the development of information and communication technologies has led to the emergence of a new direction in distance education. At present, great attention is paid to the current work of distance learning in educational institutions and universities of the Republic. At the same time, the development of science and technology, the change in the composition of knowledge, skills, qualifications and the constant increase in the volume are characterized by the high demands on today's specialists. Distance learning is the implementation of the relationship between teacher and student in the learning process on the basis of the use of modern information and communication technologies.

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